

**Parallel lawmaking as a protected object of copyright in
most countries of Europe and the USA**

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Annotation: The trend towards a simplistic approach to assessing copyrightability contributes to a general reduction in requirements for originality of works and, in a number of states, leads to the granting of national copyright protection to works with a low level of creativity and duplicate works. Works with an insignificant level of creativity in the European doctrine are synonymously called "small coin", works "with minor changes" or works "with insignificant authorship". This concept is traditionally applied to intellectual products with a minimum creative component, which gives reason to classify such objects as the "lower limit of copyright protection". Works with a low level of creativity in different countries may include photographic works, computer programs and databases, geographical maps and plans, catalogs, brochures and slogans, descriptions of driving directions, decorative and applied products (furniture, lamps, fashionable clothes, make-up etc.), technical diagrams and drawings, telephone directories and other such compilations, program guides and pop music products.

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In the legal orders of European countries, the attitude towards the issue of parallel law-making and, accordingly, to repeated works is not the same. The legal doctrine of Italy is dominated by opinions against recognizing repeated works as protectable, in support of which the following arguments are formulated: firstly, the protection of repeated works introduces chaos into the system of copyright

protection, since the author of the first work is charged with the obligation to prove not only the fact that the repeated work coincides with their own, but also the bad faith behavior of the repeated author; secondly, the recognition of the copyrightability of repeated works indirectly leads to an increase in the terms of protection of copyrighted works in excess of those established by law.

In some European countries (Germany, Spain), the possibility of parallel creation is recognized, and repeated works are considered to be protected. Thus, in accordance with Spanish law enforcement practice and doctrine, a work will be considered duplicate and protected by copyright in the event that it is possible to prove the absence of the fact of illegal borrowing, manifested in the conscious copying by the repeated author of the content of the primary work or imitation of the primary author. In Germany, a repeated work is also subject to copyright protection, however, it will be recognized as copyrightable only if the author of the repeated work not only did not intentionally violate the copyrights of others (direct copying), but also did not do so as a result of an unconscious desire to imitate (indirect copying). Thus, under the law of Germany, a repeated work will receive protected status if it can be established that the author of the repetition could not have previously familiarized himself with the original and created his work independently of the author of the original. At the same time, this approach is criticized by representatives of the German doctrine as violating the exclusivity of copyright.

Competition disputes between original and reprints are frequently heard in the courts of the United Kingdom and the United States of America. For the purpose of establishing the possibility of recognizing a repeated work as protected, a doctrine of copying has been developed. If the court determines that the repeated work is the result of illegal use of the original (full or partial copy), then the copyright of the original author is recognized as infringed, and the repeated object is recognized as unprotectable. In the opposite situation, that is, if the court establishes that there was no copying, the repeated object is recognized as a copyrightable work. The criteria for establishing the fact of copying for different types of works have their own characteristics, which can be seen in the acts of law enforcement of American and English courts. Also, in the decisions of the courts of Great Britain and the

United States, one can find an indication of the need to perform the following additional actions when considering disputes about the copyrightability of repeated works:

- to investigate "three possible assumptions" about the presence of signs of participation of the repeated author in the illegal process of copying the original - "conscious copying", "subconscious copying", "indirect copying";
- if the fact of any of the forms of copying of the original work is established, to determine how significant is the part illegally borrowed from the original work.

To establish the fact of copyright infringement of the original musical work, the following two elements must be met: "Firstly, there must be a clear objective similarity between the original work and the repeated work that infringes the copyright on it, and, secondly, the repeated work must be based on the original work, the copyright of which it infringes." In order to establish the unprotectability of a repeated work, it must be recognized that it has been copied from the original in full or in significant part. If it is established that the work was created by the second author independently, independently of the original work, there will be no copyright infringement. At the same time, the Russian doctrine presents separate opinions that contradict the stable scientific concept and law enforcement practice of non-recognition of repeated works in the Russian Federation. Supporters of the possibility of legitimate parallel creativity (V.Ya. Ionas, M.V. Labzin, Kh.O. Metov, E.A. Sviridova) allow cases of creating "the same results of creativity of two independent authors", emphasizing that "although the share such a possibility is extremely small and cannot be ruled out. Supporters of the concept specify that in a situation of parallel creativity, we are not talking about works with a traditionally high level of creativity: it is impossible to accidentally write in parallel with F.M. Dostoevsky's novel "Crime and Punishment" or with S.S. Prokofiev music for the ballet "Romeo and Juliet". However, advocates argue, copyright does not preclude the protection of simpler, repeatable objects that are also works of art, albeit of little value: for example, a photograph of a famous architectural structure such as the Moscow Kremlin or the Eiffel Tower from almost any angle is likely, already once and by someone was made.

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Back in the Soviet period of jurisprudence, supporters of the concept of the legitimacy of parallel creativity insisted: “It is quite obvious that as society develops, the number of works is growing rapidly. This, in turn, leads to the fact that fundamentally different works, even theoretically, should become less and less. The trend of recognizing copyrighted works with a low level of creativity can also be traced in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The positive side of the development of this trend for our republic can only be called the potential opportunity to generate the effect of harmonization of legislation on the issue of types of objects protected by copyright with the legislation of the states of Europe and the United States, which would be relevant for the regulation of cross-border copyright relations.

If we agree with different criteria for determining the level of creativity (significant, minor or other) for different types of works, this will violate the unity of the concept of "protectable work" and may indirectly lead to negative consequences: to give hypertrophied significance to the classification of types of works and make its practical application non-functional, because the boundaries between the genres in which works are created can be fluid and blurred.